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Case Report

Osteoma of the External Auditory Canal: A Case Report and Review of Literature

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ABSTRACT

Osteomas of the external auditory canal are considered clinically to be discrete, benign, pedunculated bone lesions arising along the tympanosquamous suture. They present as solitary, unilateral, and slow-growing tumors. It is usually asymptomatic, but symptoms can arise if a canal obstruction occurs. We report an osteoma occurring in the external auditory canal of a 14-year-old female patient who presented to the ENT Outpatient clinic with a 1-year history of progressive hearing loss affecting the right ear. On physical examination, the right external auditory canal was completely occluded by a hard mass, which was fixed and covered with wax. The Osteoma was removed surgically through the transcanal approach. Histopathological findings confirmed osteoma.

Key words: Osteomas, external auditory canal, hearing loss

INTRODUCTION

External auditory canal (EAC) osteomas are rare, benign bony neoplasms that occur in a wide range of patients. [1] While chronic irritation and inflammation have been suggested as causal factors in several cases, there is insufficient data to support these suspicions. [2, 3] Diagnosis is made based on a combination of clinical history and examination, radiographic imaging, and histopathology. [4] Osteomas of the EAC are usually found incidentally, unilateral, and solitary. It may occur in any part of the temporal bone, with the EAC being the most common site. EAC osteoma commonly arises from tympanosquamous or tympanomastoid sutures beside the bony-cartilaginous junction. [5] The cause remains unknown. Distinguishing between osteoma and exostosis of the EAC has become controversial over the last few decades. But both of these lesions are found to be incidental. [6] Symptoms of both lesions include vertigo, paroxysmal tinnitus, sensorineural hearing loss, trigeminal neuralgia, and pain. Exostoses consist of parallel, concentric layers of subperiosteal bone with abundant osteocytes on histopathology. [3, 5] Histopathologically, EAC osteomas are covered with periosteum and squamous epithelium, and consist of lamellated bone surrounding fibrovascular channels with

minimal osteocytes. [6, 7] Fibroosseous lesion of the EAC showed dense fibrous tissue admixed with mineralized osteoid material. Hence, in 1979, Graham concluded that the presence or absence of a fibrovascular channel is the distinguishing feature between exostoses and osteoma. Osteomas have historically been compared and contrasted with exostoses of the EAC. While they share similarities, in some cases, it is possible to distinguish the two bony neoplasms based on clinical history and radiographic studies. [8, 9] On computed tomography (CT) scan, an osteoma appears as a single, unilateral, pedunculated hyperdense mass that originates from the tympanosquamous or tympanomastoid suture line and extends into the internal auditory canal space. [4, 5] Exostoses appear as multiple, bilateral, broad-based, and smooth-bordered hyperdense lesions protruding into the internal auditory canal. [5, 8] CT reveals a hyperdense, pedunculated mass arising from the tympanosquamous suture and lateral to the isthmus. [5] Arguments remain in the literature as to whether basic histopathology can distinguish osteomas of the EAC from exostoses. Surgical excision is the standard treatment for EAC osteomas; however, close observation is considered acceptable in asymptomatic patients. [10]

CASE REPORT

A 14-year-old female patient presented to the ENT Outpatient clinic with a 1-year history of progressive hearing loss affecting the right ear. The patient has no history of otorrhea, Otalgia, tinnitus, or vertigo. On physical examination, the right EAC was completely occluded by a hard mass, which was fixed and covered with wax.

Puretone audiometry revealed moderate Conductive hearing loss in the right ear with a pure tone average of 42.5 dB and an air-bone gap of >15 dB (Figure 1) and normal hearing in

the left ear. CT scan of the temporal bone showed a unilateral, pedunculated 1.1 cm × 1.5 cm hyperdense mass filling and occluding the right EAC, arising from the tympanomastoid suture (Figure 2). Bilateral tympanic membranes, middle ear ossicles, cochlear, and semicircular canals were normal.

Preliminary diagnosis of right EAC osteoma was made. The patient subsequently underwent excision of the right ear canal mass by transcanal approach. Xylocaine adrenaline was infiltrated around the lesion and base to reduce intraoperative bleeding. The mass originated from the posterosuperior part of the outer half of the canal. The skin flap lateral to the stalk was raised, and the peduncle was fractured and removed. The remaining bony projection of the stalk was cleared using a high-speed drill. The flap was then repositioned. The EAC was packed with gauze and chloramphenicol ointment to prevent infection. Histopathological findings show an irregularly arranged lamellated cancellous bone with abundant fibrovascular channels, overall features suggestive of osteoma.

Postoperatively, the patient did well, was followed up for 6 months, and there was no evidence of recurrence, and the patient has normal hearing bilaterally.

DISCUSSION

Osteomas are regarded as bony lesions that show a predilection for the EAC, mastoid cortex, facial bones, and mandible. [1] Osteomas of the EAC are considered benign tumors as they are non-invasive; however, they can cause significant symptoms due to mass effect and auditory canal obstruction. [2-4]

Clinically, an osteoma of the EAC is usually a solitary, pedunculated bony growth attached to the tympanosquamous or tympanomastoid suture line, superficial to the isthmus,

Figure 1: Audiogram of the right ear with pure tone average of 42.5 dB and air bone gap of >15 dB.

Figure 2: CT scan of the right temporal bone showing a 1.1 cm × 1.5 cm ovoid bony mass in the right external auditory canal.

benign in nature but prone to progressive growth and secondary obstruction of the EAC. Occasionally, they may be small, multiple, and asymptomatic.

Osteoma should be discriminated from exostoses. Exostoses arise bilaterally in response to repeated cold-water stimulation of the bony external canal and are usually multiple, with a broad base. Osteomas, in contrast, are usually solitary pedunculated masses of unknown etiology and histopathologically different from exostoses. [5, 6] Sheehy [3] reported that out of the 16 operations done to remove a solitary osteoma involving the EAC. Three (18.8%) of these patients were under 15 years of age.

Interestingly, our case is a 14-year-old who presented as a typical hyperdense lesion on a high-resolution CT scan.

External auditory canal osteomas are removed microscopically through transcanal, postauricular, and endaural approaches. A small pedunculated lesion located lateral to the isthmus can be removed directly through transcanal, while the other approaches are recommended for a big, broad-based lesion located more medially. Recently, quite many otorhinolaryngologists have adopted transcanal endoscopic ear surgery. Chen et al. published a case series on the outcomes of endoscopic management of EAC osteoma using two methods of direct removal with and without a skin flap. [10]

CONCLUSIONS

External auditory osteoma should be considered as a differential diagnosis in a case of a lobulated hard mass in the EAC. It may appear as an ovoid mass on CT of the temporal bone.

CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from parents for the publication of this case report and all associated images.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION

All authors have significantly contributed to the work, whether by following the case at the bedside, conducting literature searches, drafting, revising, or critically reviewing the article. They have given their final approval of the version to be published, have agreed with the journal to which the article has been submitted, and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

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